

Prioritising Indigenous Livestock Breeds Grazing

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Pajuna cow herd in Sierra Nevada National Park, Aldeire, Granada.

Prioritising the access of autochthonous livestock breeds in mountain rural areas is a key measure for promoting biodiversity conservation, ecosystem resiliency, counteract rural land management and increasing their sustainability. Andalusia, characterised by its great biogeographical diversity, has autochthonous livestock breeds such as the Pajuna cow essential for the maintenance of the ecological and cultural balance in the region. The Pajuna cow, adapted to the climatic and geographical conditions of the Andalusian mountain areas (such as the high biodiverse Sierra Nevada mountain) and specifically, is currently in serious danger of extinction. Pajuna cow has specific morphological characteristics adapted to the mountain area ecosystem such as the high mobility and resistance that allow them to have access to pastures or the low size associated with low maintenance needs in the forage shortcoming periods and the reduction or soil impact on areas of high biological interest, such as Los Borreguiles de Sierra Nevada.

The valuation by a public entity on environmental values, beyond the purely economic ones, implies the recognition of the need to generate active policies able to preserve high ecological value areas, reduce hazards such as desertification or forest fires and counteracting negative demographic trends of rural population. A good example of policy implementation to foster agroforestry was carried out by the municipality of Aldeire (Sierra Nevada National Park, Granada, Spain) is supporting a sustainability public pasture action named 'Promotion of the Pajuna breed in Monte de Aldeire' based by developing a tool periodically awarding adequate public pasture management based on a two-criteria assessment that increases the agreed price for grazing. The economic and the Pajuna breed preservation criteria awards for 6 and 4 points above the initial agreed price, respectively. For the second criterium, if the number of heads of Pajuna breed in the herd is over the 20, 50 or 100%, the shepherd is awarded by 1, 2 and 4 points, respectively. The criteria resulted in a positive impact for both the grazing of the Aldeire mountain area and promotion of the Pajuna, thus reinforcing the role of livestock farming in the fight against forest fire and climate change.

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